
Household Telecommunications Expenditure in Australia

Robert Breunig and Owen McCarthy (2019)
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Key findings

We use the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey and the Household Expenditure Survey (HES) of the Australian Bureau of Statistics to:

- show that household telecommunications expenditure in Australia behaves like a necessity.
- develop measures of “telecommunications inadequacy” and “unsustainable telecommunications expenditure”.
- show that inadequacy and unsustainability are correlated with measures of disadvantage.
- show that “unsustainable telecommunications expenditure” is correlated with financial stress.
- show that very few households experience “telecommunications inadequacy.”

What we knew

- Communication via the internet or mobile telephone has become an essential element in daily life and an important element in social and labour market participation, educational attainment, and health and wellbeing.
- Importantly for low income individuals, these forms of communication are increasingly used to access necessities such as government programs, benefits and medical test results.
- Low income households may face barriers to participation in the digital economy if they spend too little on telecommunications—risking exclusion from the benefits of connectedness—or if they spend too much on telecommunications and risk having to cut back on other essential items (eg. food, energy, social activities).
- Previous research on telecommunications in Australia suggests that digital ability, affordability and access to internet services have improved for the average household in recent years, but some vulnerable groups may be spending a larger share of their income on telecommunications services than the average household.

What we do

- We use waves 6 to 15 of the HILDA survey and the 2009-10 and 2015-16 releases of the HES to look at telecommunications expenditure patterns in Australia.
- We estimate a simple model of the share of income spent on telecommunications services, controlling for household characteristics such as income and household size.
- We propose new measures to assist with the monitoring of two distinct groups of low income households who may face barriers to participation in the digital economy. We identify households with household income less than half the median, and within that group, define:
 1. ‘Low income, high spending households’ as those households with telecommunications expenditure as a share of income at more than three times the median. These households potentially have “unsustainable telecommunications expenditure”.

2. ‘Low income, low spending households’ as those households with telecommunications expenditure as a share of income at less than half the median. These households potentially suffer from “telecommunications inadequacy”.

What we know now

- Expenditure on telecommunications services behaves like a core necessity such as food, which means consumers will only alter their telecommunications consumption by a small amount as income changes. As a result, when income falls, the proportion of total expenditure allocated to telecommunications services rises.
- While telecommunications services in Australia have become more affordable on average, there are some groups who spend a larger proportion of their income on telecommunications services.
- Households in lower income deciles, households with youth or young adults, and households located in rural or remote areas spend more on telecommunications relative to their income than other households.
- Low income households spending a small proportion of their income on telecommunications services are more likely to have members aged 65 or older or who are in disadvantaged groups such as those with poor English speaking skills or long term health conditions, or those who are unemployed or not in the labour force.
 - They are also more likely to be in receipt of welfare in the form of the Age Pension or Disability Support Pension. However, Newstart Allowance recipients are not more likely to exhibit this spending pattern.
- Low income households spending a large proportion of their income on telecommunications services are more likely to report financial difficulty in the subsequent period and to have household members in disadvantaged groups, such as those with long term health conditions or poor English speaking skills, or those who are Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander, unemployed or not in the labour force.

What this means for policy

- There is a potential risk for low income households of reduced participation as communications services become increasingly necessary to engage with society and the economy, and as digital transformation moves government services online.
- If low income earners are unable to afford communications services, they may not be able to utilise online services to their full extent.

Caveats

- Data limitations mean that our two measures only identify a potential for unaffordable expenditure or exclusion from the digital economy. Linked data which provides information on household characteristics along with information on the quantity and quality of communications services consumed would allow for more precise measures and better identification of at-risk groups.

Where to now?

- There is a need to understand and assess the risks from unaffordable internet access among low income households in the context of welfare, business and community services moving online.

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- Future work should identify the usage requirements of low income individuals or households accessing essential services, and determine whether appropriate bundles of telecommunications services which are available in the market are affordable.

More information

- Get the full working paper at: https://crawford.anu.edu.au/sites/default/files/uploads/crawford01_cap_anu_edu_au/2019-07/telexp_v3.docx or the published version at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2019.101837>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
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